

Effect of Kaniadakis Information on High e/T In Two Body Collisions

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Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics is linked with two body collisions $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ ((1)) for $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$. Taking \ln of both sides yields a $\ln(p(e_i))$ such that information is conserved on both sides of ((1)). In the Fermi-Dirac or Bose-Einstein cases, one has instead: $p(e_i) (1-p(e_k)) p(e_j) (1-p(e_l)) = p(e_k) (1-p(e_i)) p(e_l) (1-p(e_j))$. Then it is $\ln(p(e_i) / (1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/T$ instead of $\ln(p(e_i))$. One again thinks in terms of two body collisions.

In the Kaniadakis case, $F(p(e_i)) = 1/(2k) (p^k - p^{-k})$. Given that $e_{ave} = E/N = \sum_i p(e_i) e_i$, we try to consider two body collisions in the Kaniadakis scenario. We argue that like in the MB, FD or BE cases, one should have a function G such that $\ln(G(p(e))) = F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$, where $G(p(e_i))$ is an effective collision probability. In the $e/T \ll 1$ limit, $p(e_i)$ becomes a MB distribution (not just in the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit), but in the $e_i/T \gg 1$ limit one has: $p(\text{effective}) = p(e_i) \exp(-e_i/T) (e_i/T)^{-1/k}$. For $k < 0$, we argue that factor multiplying $p(e_i)$ is less than 1. Given that $p(e_i) > p(e_i)_{MB}$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$, the extra factor $(e_i/T)^{-1/k}$ allows for higher values of $p(e_i)$ for $e_i/T \gg 1$ (than in the MB case) because the extra factor is less than 1. Overall, the effective probability plays the same role as $p(e_i)_{MB}$ in collisions, but must arise as a physical consequence of the reactions which occur. Thus, one argues that nature allows for higher $p(e_i)$ values for $e_i/T \gg 1$ (than in the MB case) because the reaction is more complicated such that a special factor arises which reduces $p(e_i)$ in the reaction balance equation.

Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) Case

In an MB gas, $p(e_i)$ is the probability to find a particle with e_i . One might at first not consider the nature of collisions and just take $p(e_i)$ as an experimental result. $p(e_i)$, however, follows from:

$$p(e_i) p(e_j) = p(e_k) p(e_l) \text{ if } e_i+e_j = e_k+e_l \quad ((1))$$

((1)) is a reaction balance equation related to collisions. Thus, $p(e_i)$ is not only linked with the number of particles with e_i , but also with elastic two body collisions because the second equation in ((1)) is a conservation of energy in an elastic collision.

It is well-known that successful collisions may be subject to more complicated physical restrictions than ((1)). In particular, in the Fermi-Dirac case, one cannot have an e_i scatter into an e_k state if there is already a particle in the e_k state.

In a previous note, we argued that ((1)) is equivalent to $N_i N_j = N_k N_l$, where $N_i = N p(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . Then, $N_i N_j$ is the statistical count of all possible $N_i N_j$ pairings which is a conserved value. Similarly then in the FD case, one should have all possible collision pairings, but now N_i does not mean that an e_i particle collides successfully. Rather:

$$N_i (1 - N_k) = \text{number successful pairings of an } e_i \text{ with a neighbour which is not an } e_k \quad ((2))$$

Similarly, $N_j (1-N_i) =$ number of successful pairing of an e_j with a neighbour which is not an e_i

Then, the total number of successful collisions of e_i, e_j to e_k, e_l is:

$N_i(1-N_k) N_j (1-N_l)$ and this must equal $N_k(1-N_i) N_l(1-N_j)$ due to time reversal balance ((3))

As a result,

$\ln(p(e_i) / (1-p(e_i))) = -e_i/ T$ i the FD case. ((4))

A similar result holds for the Bose-Einstein scenario.

Kaniadakis Case

We argue that one should be able to think of the Kaniadakis case in terms of two body elastic collisions, especially because $k \rightarrow 0$ yields the MB results. We suggest, however, that like in the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, one requires:

$\ln(G(p(e_i))) = F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (5) For the Kaniadakis case: $F(p) = 1/2k (p \text{ power } k - p \text{ power } -k)$ ((5))

$-1 < k < 1$ ((6))

Thus, $G(p(e_i)) =$ effective probability for a successful collision of an e_i .

A simple solution is: $G = \exp(F(p(e_i))) = \exp(-e_i/T)$ and one may consider:

$G(p(e_i)) G(p(e_j)) = G(p(e_k)) G(p(e_l))$ for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$ as in the MB, FD and BE cases ((7))

Writing: $G(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) \exp(F(p(e_i))) / p(e_i) = p(e_i) \exp(-e_i/T) / p(e_i)$ ((8))

one then sees how the MB $p(e_i)$ is modified in collision.

If one considers $e_i/T \ll 1$, the $p(e_i) \rightarrow \exp(-e_i/T)$, i.e. the MB result. It is not simply the $k \rightarrow 0$ limit which yields the MB result. In that case,

$\exp(-e_i/T) / p(e_i) = 1$ ((9))

and one has a Maxwell-Boltzmann type of two body elastic collision scenario.

In the $e_i/T \gg 1$ case:

$p(e_i) \exp(-e_i/T) (e_i/T)^{-1/k}$ because $p(e_i) = (e_i/T)^{1/k}$ ((10))

Here we use $k < 0$ because one wishes $p(e_i)$ to drop as a power law for $e_i/T \gg 1$. One may see that

$$\exp(-e_i/T) (e_i/T)^{-1/k} < 1 \quad ((11))$$

In other words, one may have a higher value of $p(e_i)$ Kaniadakis for $e_i/T \gg 1$ (compared to the MB value) because the effective successful collision probability is damped by the factor $\exp(-e_i/T) (e_i/T)^{-1/k}$. Thus, the collision behaviour in a Kaniadakis elastic collision is one which allows higher $p(e_i)$ values for $e_i/T \gg 1$ (than in the MB case) to effectively behave as if they had lower probability overall in a collision. This feature, however, is dependent on the properties of the collisions of which one might originally be unaware. In particular, in the MB case, one simply suggests that $p(e_i)$ is the probability for an e_i to appear and that it will automatically have a successful collision without any enhancements or reductions. Such is not the case in situations in which the Kaniadakis (or FD and BE) distributions apply.

Further Considerations

To see the specific effect of the reaction, one may examine:

$$p(e_i) \exp(-e_i/T) \left(\sqrt{1 + k e_i^2 / T} - k e_i / T \right)^{-1/k} \quad (\text{where } k < 0) \quad ((12))$$

$p(e_i)$ represents the probability to have an e_i present to collide, but a successful collision involves the extra factor in ((12)). Thus, there must be some physics of the reaction which gives rise to the extra factor. The simplest argument to suggest a $p(e_i)$ which depends on a single parameter k such that for $e_i/T \ll 1$, one has the MB distribution and for $e_i/T \gg 1$, one has a power law $(e_i/T)^{1/k}$ ($k < 0$). The Tsallis distribution, however, also satisfies these two criteria, but relies on a constraint: $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i^q = \text{number}$ instead of the usual $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = \text{eave}$ used in the Kaniadakis, MB, FD and BE cases. One may have two distributions:

$$1/(1-q) \left(1 - (1-q) e_i/T \right)^{1/(1-q)} \quad ((13a)) \text{ and}$$

$$\left(\sqrt{1 + k e_i^2 / T} - k e_i / T \right)^{1/k} \quad (k < 0) \quad ((13b))$$

which yield the MB result for $e_i/T \ll 1$ and $(e_i/T)^{1/k}$ number of $e_i/T \gg 1$. Why should the first be associated with a constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i^q$ and the second with $\sum_i p(e_i) = \text{eave}$? We have argued in previous notes that it is because in the second case (Kaniadakis) $p(e_i) p(-e_i) = 1$ (p unnormalized) whereas this does not hold for the Tsallis scenario.

If one considers two body scattering, then $p(e_i)$ represents the probability to have an e_i particle present. $p(e_i)p(-e_i)$ should mathematically be the probability to have no particle present and so should be a constant, if one takes two body scattering seriously. This does not hold for ((13a)), i.e. the Tsallis case, but holds for ((13b)), the Kaniadakis scenario. Thus, we argue that the Kaniadakis scenario is amenable to a two body elastic scattering analysis. It is a somewhat complicated extra scattering factor seen in ((12)), however, that is needed to ensure that one has the MB case for $e_i/T \ll 1$, $(e_i/T)^{1/k}$ negative number for $e_i/T \gg 1$ and $p(e_i) p(-e_i) = 1$

(unnormalized p). In the literature, $p(e_i) p(-e_i) = 1$ is sometimes attributed to particle-hole scenarios, but we argue that it is an essential feature required for two body elastic collisions to occur.

Tsallis Scenario

The Tsallis scenario is linked with a constraint:

$$\sum_i e_i p(e_i)^q = \text{number} \quad (13)$$

As a result, we do not consider a $p(e_i)$ as carrying an energy e_i as in the MB, FD, BE or even Kaniadakis cases. Rather it is $p(e_i)^q$ which carries e_i . Physically, we suggest that this means that an e_i is not produced unless one has $p(e_i)^q$, i.e. multiple AND situations. As a result, the simple two body collision picture does not seem to apply directly to the Tsallis picture because there must be q events (AND probability events) involving $p(e_i)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the MB, FD and BE cases are all readily associated with two body elastic scattering. In the MB case, the probability for two particles to scatter is $p(e_i) p(e_j)$, i.e. only the presence of each type of energy particle is needed to ensure a successful reaction. Such is not the case for the FD or BE scenarios. There, the energy value of the nearest neighbour particles also plays a role. Thus, one has a modified expression: $G(p(e_i)) G(p(e_j)) = G(p(e_k)) G(p(e_l))$ for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$. We suggest that a similar situation should hold for the Kaniadakis case, i.e.

$$\ln(G(p(e_i))) = -e_i/T = F(p(e_i)) \text{ where } F(p(e_i)) = 1/(2k) (p^k - p^{-k}) \text{ holds}$$

One then has: $G = \exp(-e_i/T) = \exp(F)$ and the $p(e_i)$ of the MB situation becomes:

$$\text{Effective collision probability} = p(e_i) G(p(e_i)) / p(e_i) = p(e_i) \exp(-e_i/T) / p(e_i)$$

For $e_i/T \ll 1$, $p(e_i)$ becomes the MB $\exp(-e_i/T)$ and the effective collision probability is the same as the MB one.

For $e_i/T \gg 1$, one has $p(e_i) = (e_i/T)^{1/k}$ where $k < 0$ and the effective probability is: $p(e_i) \exp(-e_i/T) (e_i/T)^{-1/k} \exp(-e_i/T) (e_i/T)^{-1/k} < 1$ in this case, so there is a factor less than 1 which allow $p(e_i)$ Kaniadakis to be larger than $p(e_i)$ MB for large e_i values. Physically, however, the reaction must allow for this by ensuring that restrictions exist such that the $\exp(-e_i/T)/p(e_i)$ factor arise, (just as special factors arise in the FD and BE cases).